

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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- Sciensano (**SCI**)

List of abbreviations

AJCC, American joint committee on cancer
 AML, acute myeloid leukemia
 CHIP, clonal hematopoiesis of indeterminate potential
 CLL, chronic lymphocytic leukemia
 CNV, copy number variation
 CRC, colorectal cancer
 CRO, contract research organization
 dPCR, digital polymerase chain reaction
 FFPE, formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded
 GL, germline
 HM, hematological malignancies
 LB, liquid biopsy

LumA, luminal A type breast cancer
MBL, monoclonal B lymphocytosis
MRD, minimal residual disease
MSI, microsatellite instability
MTA/DTA, material and data transfer agreements
NED, no evidence of disease
NGS, next-generation sequencing
NSCLC, non-small cell lung cancer
PBMNC, peripheral blood mononuclear cell
SNV, single nucleotide variant
SOM, somatic
TMB, tumor mutational burden
VAF, variant allele frequency
VUS, variant of unknown significance

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Summary

D23 is the last one of three closely related deliverables planned for WP7 being released in rapid succession. WP7 established four clinical pilots focused on non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), colorectal cancer (CRC), luminal A type breast cancer (LumA), and hematological malignancies (HM). This document addresses Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) and other molecular readouts that capture individual cancer risk, e.g. Minimal Residual Disease (MRD), and familial predisposition (heritable genomic alterations). We provide examples of raw data that attest to the variety of technical readouts and clinical applications. NGS readouts include genomic alterations (mutational hits) and epigenomic alterations (methyloomics and fragmentomics). More than 95% of NGS samples have been processed and analyzed as planned. The samples lagging behind belong to: (a) collections for which we were unable to complete the Data Transfer and Material Transfer Agreements (MTA/DTA), and (b) very few technical failures. NGS testing is being finalized at the time of writing.

D23 was meant to report on 40 out of 45 patients (planned enrolment) to accommodate for minor deviations from protocol. We report on more than 80 patients, >95% of successfully tested. The few samples for which no NGS data are available yet are being tested or will be tested once the MTA/DTA are finalized. D23 was submitted with a delay of about three weeks.

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Objective of the deliverable

- Foreword

D23 is the last one in a series of three closely related WP7 deliverables, being released in rapid succession. It is being released after D24 and together with D25.

D23: T7.1 - Task leader ACC.

NGS testing data. 40 evaluable patients tested, raw and curated NGS data. Link with ELBS (WP11) to address technical NGS issues.

Due Feb 28th

D24: T7.2 - Task leader ICO.

Integration of NGS and clinical data. NGS data available in the framework of clinical information.

Due Jan 31st (submitted)

D25: T7.3 - Task leader NKI-AVL.

Data transfer to WP3 for HTA evaluation.

Due Feb 28th (*This deliverable*)

In D24, and D25 the Can.HEAL Consortium provided a general overview of the clinical pilot study plan from rationale to implications. These aspects will be briefly recalled herein. In D23 we will focus on technical readouts of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) testing, and will provide concrete examples of their specific use to test Minimal Residual Disease (MRD) and genetic predisposition to cancer in specific patients.

- The WP7 pilots: design

As shown in Fig. 1, WP7 focuses on specific use cases (clinical pilots) involving colorectal cancer (CRC), non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), luminal A type breast cancer (LumA), and hematological

Fig. 1. Can.HEAL clinical pilots. Four pilots were designed. Three of them explore tissue and blood (liquid biopsy) readouts in the early setting (patients undergoing surgery with curative intent). Three solid tumors were investigated: Colorectal Cancer (CRC); Breast Cancer (BrCa), and Lung cancer (NSCLC). The fourth pilot is about the capture of gene variants associated with Clonal Hematopoiesis of indetermined Potential (CHIP) and Monoclonal B cell expansions in the hematological setting (Acute Myelogenous Leukemia and Multiple Myeloma).

malignancies (HM) associated with clonal hematopoiesis of indeterminate potential (CHIP) and/or monoclonal B lymphocytosis (MBL). Besides a shared backbone (sampling), NGS is the common technical denominator. NGS captures genomic and epigenomic alterations that define patient risk independently of (or complementary to) clinical pathological variables.

- The WP7 pilots: NGS approaches

As shown in Fig. 2, all pilots have collected clinical and/or clinical pathological data, combined with molecular data, using common strategies and tools. The sources of molecular data were germ line DNA (gDNA), somatic DNA from tumor tissue (tDNA), and circulating tumor DNA from blood plasma (ctDNA).

Fig. 2. Can.HEAL genomic tools. The 4 pilots apply 5 tools to detect germ line and cancer somatic alterations. Genomic and epigenomic readouts (yellow box) are applied to tumor DNA (tDNA), circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA), germ line DNA (gDNA). Tools are a mixture of tumor agnostic and tumor-informed approaches. Minimal Residual Disease is actively looked for. Geneticists, Hematologists, Oncologists, and Biotechnologists form a team to interpret genomic endpoints, including incidental results such as germ line alterations, Clonal Hematopoiesis, and other similar conditions. Hematology counseling is incorporated in the Can.HEAL concept. Additionally, hematologists run a separate use case. A special emphasis is placed on non-invasive approaches, particularly liquid biopsy (on ctDNA).

Testing of these three analytes was carried out with the 5 genomic tools listed in the inset of Fig. 2. Briefly, GerSom is a targeted NGS panel matching sequencing information from gDNA and tDNA to capture genomic alterations associated with familial predisposition in the former, and tumor specific alterations in the latter. Tumor-specific alterations are then used to set up bespoke digital PCR (dPCR) assays for tumor-informed search of Minimal Residual Disease (MRD) in blood. Blood is also tested by tumor-agnostic NGS panels looking for additional genomic alterations (e.g. DRAGON), as well as DNA methylation (^{CH3}ctDNA) and fragmentomic (GIPXplore) signatures. A different testing platform collects molecular data for the hematological pilot.

Work performed

Essentially all the clinical specimens have been collected (see D23 and D25). Herein, we will provide examples of MRD detection in blood (liquid biopsy) with the different platforms. We will also touch

upon germ line alterations, and will provide evidence for pre-analytical processing success despite an elaborated specimen distribution chain across EU, from the recruiting sites to the testing sites.

- Specimen distribution and testing

Can.HEAL envisages that each clinical sample is tested by different approaches and the results are then integrated to determine how multi-center collaboration may result in providing homogeneous equitable access to genomics across EU. Under this respect, the project has fulfilled its goal. Patients were recruited in four Countries: Italy, Serbia and Spain. Specimens were collected and shipped to Belgium, France, Germany, and Italy for testing, resulting in a systematic technological exchange/comparison, as intended.

Results

NGS results obtained in the different NGS platforms adopted in the CAN.Heal pilots will be described separately.

- GerSom (ACC) approach

Annex 1 (appended at the end of this document) shows a selection of raw data from one of the four clinical pilots, the one on colorectal cancer (CRC). Tissue NGS was performed on tissue DNA (tDNA) from the primary tumor of 12 patients newly diagnosed with CRC, with no radiological evidence of metastatic spread. All patients were enrolled at the time they underwent ablative surgery with curative intent. This gene alteration list is only one of several lists that may be flexibly generated by imposing different filters. In the examples provided in Annex 1, we removed all the alterations shared between germline (from PBMCs) and somatic (from the tumor) DNAs. However, this info is available in the raw data and can be easily retrieved. Therefore, genetic predisposition is captured by the GerSom NGS panel and may be made available to medical geneticists. From the NGS data in Annex 1 several conclusions may be drawn.

- NGS results in highly structured data. Taking advantage of semi-automated filters a pre-annotated genomic overview of genomic alterations may be generated, pre-classified for origin (germ line or somatic), basic molecular info (type of alteration), potential clinical relevance, and actionability (e.g. ESCAT scale). These data are ready for upload into common data sharing/analysis platforms (see D25)
- In this specific case, the list has been generated to look for MRD, e.g. to capture tumor specific alterations that are likely to be adaptively selected during the post-surgery period and may then guide adjuvant therapy (escalation and de-escalation). Our criteria were as follows:

a) selection of tumor specific (gDNA⁻/somDNA⁺) SNVs

b) selection ranking: actionable>pathogenic>VUS (variant of unknown significance), e.g. prioritization of major cancer drivers, particularly if potentially exploitable for treatment in future trials (e.g. adjuvant or first-line settings)

c) hi VAF (variant allele frequency) - hi tumor fraction: exceptions notwithstanding, SNVs abundant in tDNA are likely to be abundant in ctDNA

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d) exonic location: decreasing the chance of neutral selection and/or genetic drift/elimination of passenger SNVs

e) complexity of target region (e.g. discard CG-rich, repetitive regions etc)

f) selecting SNVs at genomic positions allowing easy design of custom dPCR assay

When these criteria are applied several SNVs per patient may be selected for MRD monitoring. Two examples are provided in Fig. 3 of two patients maintaining and losing, respectively, two SNVs in the post-surgery period. Based on the above premises and a large body of literature (1-5), Pt#2 is at higher risk of relapse. Moreover, it is evident by comparison between panels (a) and (b) that dPCR is a method of choice in that it detects few copies of mutated allele per ml, e.g. it achieves a sensitivity about 500 times higher than that necessary to detect ctDNA in advanced CRC.

Fig. 3. Detection of Minimal Residual Disease (MRD) by NGS and bespoke digital PCR (dPCR) in Colorectal Cancer (CRC) patients. Representative examples of dPCR custom assays to detect MRD. (a) ctDNA was obtained at the indicated times from newly diagnosed CRC patients. They have no evidence of disease except the primary tumor. ctDNA was tested by two different bespoke assays. (b) a control ctDNA obtained from a patient with metastatic CRC. Yellow: no amplification. Red: WT allele. Blue: mutated allele. Green: dPCR nanowells containing both WT and MUT allele amplimers. Copies of mutated allele per ml are shown.

- Institut Curie (IC) DRAGON platform

All plasma specimens were received at IC from the following pilot sites:

Pilot	Number of plasma samples	Number of patients
ICO	63	20
FPG	9	3

For each sample, 4mL of plasma was received, and 2mL were used for ctDNA extraction. The concentrations obtained were low, with a median of 0.05 ng/ μ l (range 0-0.44 ng/ μ l). The remaining 2mL of plasma will also be extracted in the coming weeks to maximize the ctDNA quantities obtained for NGS testing.

All samples are being tested for SNVs, CNVs, TMB and MSI status using a custom NGS panel known as DRAGON (Detection of Relevant Alterations in Genes involved in Oncogenetics by NGS), commercially available as SureSelect CD Curie CGP by Agilent. It is composed of 571 genes of interest in oncology from a diagnosis, prognosis and molecular therapy points of view. The nucleotide sequence as well as the number of copies (homozygous deletion and focal amplification) are explored. IC platform use the design of the 571 genes and an additional backbone of probes across the whole genome with an average resolution of one probe every 200 Kb. This allows to determine a ploidy and an estimated cellularity, together with a genomic profile spanning every chromosome.

- University of Tübingen (EKUT): methylomics

A special advantage of DNA methylation profiling is the possibility to get early insights into carcinogenesis. DNA methylation profiling of cell-free/circulating tumour DNA (cf/ctDNA) from liquid biopsies has been discussed as a promising approach to monitor disease progression and therapy response. Using state of the art high enzymatic methyl-sequencing combined with a targeted enrichment system for pan-cancer, we are able to achieve deep coverage with minimal DNA inputs.

The table below provides an overview of the samples received from ICO, IFO-IRE and FPG and the current status.

Provider	Announced	Received	Extracted	Sequenced
ICO	60	60	45	0
IFO-IRE (ACC)	60	51	0	0
FPG (ACC)	9	9	0	0

The standard protocol is based on the MagMAX cell-free DNA Isolation kit from ThermoFisher. As of this moment we extracted cfDNA from 45 samples (3 timepoints from 15 patients) received from ICO, whereas the remaining samples are being shipped. The adjacent figure gives an overview of

cfDNA concentrations measured in ng per µl by Qubit dsDNA HS. Overall, the sample pre-surgery (PREIQ) had lower DNA concentrations as those at 4 weeks (4W) or 12 weeks (12W). Further, samples at 12W had slightly lower levels of DNA as those at 4W. Additionally we performed Agilent’s cell-free DNA ScreenTape analysis with a predefined range of 50bp-700bp for cfDNA. All of our samples had more than 70% of material in that range, indicating that the samples are of high quality and are well suited for downstream analysis without additional clean up steps.

Fig. 4. Methylomics: pre-analytical testing. cfDNA amounts of serial blood drawing

- **Katholic University of Leuven (KUL): fragmentomics by GIPXplore**

As outlined in a recent review (5), fragmentomic is an appealing alternative to, and possibly an ideal complement of, conventional, tumor-informed, mutation-based MRD systems like GerSom (see above). An overview of the number of samples received and pre-analytical processing data of samples obtained from the ICO (Spain) lung cancer pilot is provided in Table 1 below and Annex 2.

- Table 1: Current state on the sample cohort from ICO

Number of samples received	59
Number of samples extracted	59
Number of samples sequenced	48
Number of tests failed	0

Samples were received as frozen plasma aliquots. They were pooled for cfDNA extraction using the Promega Maxwell® RSC ccfDNA LV Plasma Kit, to a final volume of 55 µl. Concentrations were measured by Qubit™ 1X dsDNA High Sensitivity (HS) kit and were remarkably similar, with few outliers, indirectly suggesting sample conservation during shipment and pre-analytical processing. cfDNA concentration of the extracted cfDNA is presented in Annex 2. Library were prepared by an adapted Twist Library Preparation protocol, pooled together and hybridized with in-house developed comprehensive gene panel, encompassing > 400 cancer-specific genes. The remaining libraries were pooled together for shallow whole-genome sequencing (sWGS). Hybridized captured and sWGS pools were sequenced on a NovaSeq X Plus. Targeted deep sequencing data is subsequently analyzed using in-house developed pipelines to identify single-nucleotide variants (SNVs), indels, fusions and additional molecular biomarkers, including microsatellite instability (MSI) and tumor mutation burden (TMB). Genome-wide copy number profiling and in-house developed fragmentomic analyses are performed on sWGS data to identify underlying cancer-specific patterns in cfDNA serving as additional biomarkers.

- **Charité (CHAR): hematology**

Clonal Hematopoiesis of Indeterminate Potential (CHIP) is increasingly recognized as a significant biomarker for both hematologic malignancies and cardiovascular diseases. Understanding its implications facilitates early intervention, thereby reducing the risk of life-threatening conditions.

1. Analysis of Acute Myeloid Leukemia (AML) Patients:

In a study involving 20 AML patients, clonal evolution was observed throughout the disease progression. NGS of bone marrow (BM) blasts was conducted at diagnosis, during relapse following chemotherapy, and again during relapse after allogeneic stem cell transplantation. Notably, 80% of the patients studied had CHIP mutations at diagnosis.

Clonal evolution involves the transformation of treatment-sensitive cells into treatment-resistant ones. Studying this process is crucial for understanding therapy resistance mechanisms and developing strategies to prevent relapse and improve patient outcomes.

2. Analysis of Multiple Myeloma (MM) Patients:

In a separate cohort of 20 MM patients, both bone marrow DNA (from CD138+ cells) and circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) were analyzed.

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NGS demonstrated a high concordance of clonal somatic mutations between liquid biopsy and tumor biopsy (specifically CD138-enriched bone marrow). However, the presence of additional mutations detected solely in ctDNA suggests an increased heterogeneity of MM clones. A high tumor mutational burden was observed to have significant prognostic implications. The findings confirm the potential of liquid biopsy in personalized medicine, offering significant promise for cancer detection, prognostic prediction, minimal residual disease monitoring, and treatment stratification.

Furthermore, a significant majority of MM patients exhibited common CHIP mutations in ctDNA, with *DNMT3A* mutations found in 88% of patients, *TET2* in 41%, and *ASXL1* in 6%. Importantly, these mutations persist after successful therapy and do not contradict remission.

It is known that CHIP itself is not a disease but a risk factor and is a common phenomenon associated with aging. However, the presence of these mutations gives a higher potential risk of developing blood cancer and cardiovascular diseases. In addition, the presence of CHIP mutations is of interest in the context of allogeneic stem cell transplantation and familial cancer syndromes.

- Proficiency testing and connection with the European Liquid Biopsy Society (ELBS)

Fig. 5. Quality assurance of MRD testing by dPCR. Testing of 30 samples distributed in the context of an EQA program of the Danish ctDNA Society. Regression between expected and detected amounts of ctDNA and violin plot of raw data are shown side by side. The Can.HEAL Consortium is particularly grateful to Professor Claus Lindbjerg Andersen, Group Leader and Director of the National Danish ctDNA Research Center, and Dr. Maria Maria Hønholt Jørgensen, Ph.D. student, Aarhus University, Denmark for including Can.HEAL in the proficiency program and careful supervision, data sharing, and collaboration.

Intrinsic to the Can.HEAL concept is the idea that any multicenter pilot should include a robust quality assurance. Although we have not implemented this approach systematically, we took advantage of an established set of reference materials and had one testing site participating in a wide External Quality Assurance (EQA) program initiated by Danish ctDNA Society and later extended to the Can.HEAL project as a proof of principle, in collaboration with the European Liquid Biopsy

Society (ELBS). From the results shown in Fig.5, it may be concluded that although mutation calling is largely concordant, there is a suboptimal correspondence in this set of 30 samples between the expected and observed VAF values, with few false positives (although at extremely low, barely detectable levels). Moreover, there is a systematic VAF overestimation by the local test compared to the reference values provided by the EQA organizer. This prompted the Can.HEAL group to a careful troubleshooting. It was found that the testing team had switched to a new dPCR platform in the understanding that the assays previously utilized on an older platform would run seamlessly on the

new equipment. These discrepancies were reported to the manufacturer who started a detailed in-house testing. Contrary to initial recommendations, the manufacturer now recommends that all previous assays are optimized or replaced due to the different architecture of the amplification/detection system. These results provide proof of principle of the importance to include a solid EQA program in multi-center testing, as a measure to keep quality consistent and timely address deviation from good practices.

Main achievements and lessons learnt

Main achievements:

- Feasibility: efficient biological specimen collection/dispatch/sharing protocol across 6 EU Countries: Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Serbia, and Spain.
- Feasibility: a de-centralized, flexible Pilot architecture whereby samples may be collected and/or tested at any location in any of the above countries
- Five specialized testing platforms, no effort duplication
- Risk capture in gDNA and tDNA: all-in-one solution feasible
- Genetic counseling integration
- Solid tumors and hematology pilot deployed as standalone modules but with the possibility of hematological counseling integration
- New model of 'combinatorial' diagnostic testing, upon data consolidation: pick the best or best combination
- Centralized NGS data collection (also see D25)
- An initial EQA scheme across technologies and geographical locations (future ring trials)
- Equitable access to genomics of EU patients from served and underserved areas
- Team building, expertise exchange, collaborative efforts
- Positive outlook for pilot expansion into larger clinical trials

Limitations and lessons learnt include:

- Imperfect and asynchronous data testing in some cases
- Cost-effectiveness to be assessed
- Coordination complex

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Impact

Despite limitations, Can.HEAL WP7 pilots have been largely successful. Raw data were generated (>95% successful). It may be foreseen that the WP7 pilots and genomic platforms applied by Can.HEAL (or similar clinical studies by others) may serve as 'backbones', e.g. they may be expanded into future hi-numerosity trials. Since the role of genomics and epigenomics in early diagnosis and prevention remain a pre-paradigmatic area, EU-wide trials are needed to design future healthcare scenarios.

With very limited technical failure, most (>95%) NGS testing activities were successfully completed, and proof of principle was obtained of the Can.HEAL approach.

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Annex 1: CRC testing by the GerSOM panel

Tumor_Sample_Barcode	Hugo_Symbol	Chromosome	Variant_Classification	Variant_Type	cDNA_Change	Protein_Change	tumor_f	ClinVar_VCF_CLNSIG	CancerVar	ESCAT	InterVar	RENOVO_Class	
GERS26D055-2TAD126	WT1	chr11	Silent	SNP	c.1568G>A	p.*523*	0,478064	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26D055-1NAD126	WT1	chr11	Silent	SNP	c.1568G>A	p.*523*	0,568966	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	Likely benign	HP Benign	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	NTHL1	chr16	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.443C>T	p.A148V	0,318725	Uncertain_significance	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS2678ML-1NAD126	FLCN	chr17	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.1333G>A	p.A445T	0,503841	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	Likely benign	IP Benign	
GERS2678ML-2TAD126	FLCN	chr17	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.1333G>A	p.A445T	0,544885	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-2TAD126	TP53	chr17	Frame_Shift_Del	DEL	c.403delT	p.C135fs	0,464315	Pathogenic	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	TSC2	chr16	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.1939G>A	p.D647N	0,488544	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS262K3Z-1NAD126	TSC2	chr16	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.1939G>A	p.D647N	0,471154	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	Uncertain significance	LP Pathogenic	
GERS26D055-2TAD126	NF2	chr22	Silent	SNP	c.255T>C	p.D85D	0,527555	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26D055-1NAD126	NF2	chr22	Silent	SNP	c.255T>C	p.D85D	0,515625	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	Likely benign	HP Benign	
ERS26BVAA-2TAD126	APC	chr5	Nonsense_Mutation	SNP	c.4189G>T	p.E1397*	0,193193	.	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-2TAD126	PIK3CA	chr3	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.1093G>A	p.E365K	0,273527	Pathogenic	Tier_II_potential	IIA	.	.	
GERS26N9FG-TAD126	POLE	chr12	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.3913G>A	p.G1305R	0,395349	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-2TAD126	RET	chr10	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2071G>A	p.G691S	0,51298	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-1NAD126	RET	chr10	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2071G>A	p.G691S	0,470474	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	IB	Benign	HP Benign
GERS26KLL0-2TAD126	RET	chr10	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2071G>A	p.G691S	0,484	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26KLL0-1NAD126	RET	chr10	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2071G>A	p.G691S	0,517206	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	IB	Benign	HP Benign
GERS2678ML-1NAD126	RET	chr10	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2071G>A	p.G691S	0,480027	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	IB	Benign	HP Benign
GERS2678ML-2TAD126	RET	chr10	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2071G>A	p.G691S	0,524823	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26N9FG-TAD126	PIK3CA	chr3	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.3140A>G	p.H1047R	0,334838	Pathogenic	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
GERS2678ML-1NAD126	TSC2	chr16	Silent	SNP	c.4077C>T	p.I1359I	0,524361	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	.	Likely benign	HP Benign
GERS2678ML-2TAD126	TSC2	chr16	Silent	SNP	c.4077C>T	p.I1359I	0,552356	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	MSH2	chr2	Frame_Shift_Ins	INS	c.2592_2593insA	p.I865fs	0,49444	Pathogenic	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS262K3Z-1NAD126	MSH2	chr2	Frame_Shift_Ins	INS	c.2592_2593insA	p.I865fs	0,535088	Pathogenic	.	.	Likely pathogenic	HP Pathogenic	
GERS26N9FG-TAD126	APC	chr5	Frame_Shift_Del	DEL	c.4461delT	p.L1488fs	0,30413	Pathogenic	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26N9FG-TAD126	APC	chr5	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2585A>G	p.N862S	0,473631	Uncertain_significance	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26N9FG-1NAD126	APC	chr5	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2585A>G	p.N862S	0,488372	Uncertain_significance	.	.	Likely benign	IP Benign	
GERS26V0U3-2TAD126	ERBB2	chr17	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.1466C>T	p.P489L	0,207836	Uncertain_significance	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-2TAD126	APC	chr5	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.3511C>T	p.R1171C	0,756098	Benign/Likely_benign	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	TP53	chr17	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.473G>A	p.R158H	0,20888	Pathogenic/Likely_pathogenic	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
GERS26D055-2TAD126	MEN1	chr11	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.512G>A	p.R171Q	0,495781	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26N9FG-TAD126	APC	chr5	Nonsense_Mutation	SNP	c.637C>T	p.R213*	0,319079	Pathogenic	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
GERS26KLL0-2TAD126	APC	chr5	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.688C>T	p.R230C	0,378882	Uncertain_significance	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
GERS26KLL0-1NAD126	APC	chr5	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.688C>T	p.R230C	0,484694	Uncertain_significance	.	.	Uncertain significance	LP Pathogenic	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	BRAF	chr7	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.1040G>A	p.R347Q	0,21134	Uncertain_significance	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-2TAD126	POLE	chr12	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2224C>T	p.R742C	0,447507	Uncertain_significance	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-1NAD126	POLE	chr12	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.2224C>T	p.R742C	0,50911	Uncertain_significance	.	.	Uncertain significance	HP Pathogenic	
GERS26V0U3-2TAD126	RET	chr10	Splice_Site	SNP	c.2944C>T	p.R982C	0,508436	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-1NAD126	RET	chr10	Splice_Site	SNP	c.2944C>T	p.R982C	0,513158	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	IB	Likely benign	HP Benign
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	APC	chr5	Frame_Shift_Del	DEL	c.4385_4386delAG	p.S1465fs	0,20583	Pathogenic	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26KLL0-2TAD126	TP53	chr17	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.643A>C	p.S215R	0,362663	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
GERS26KLL0-2TAD126	ATM	chr11	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.998C>T	p.S333F	0,484444	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_II_potential	IIA	.	.	
GERS26KLL0-1NAD126	ATM	chr11	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.998C>T	p.S333F	0,476562	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	IIA	Uncertain significance	IP Benign
GERS26KLL0-2TAD126	APC	chr5	Frame_Shift_Ins	INS	c.3900_3901insA	p.T1301fs	0,290976	Pathogenic/Likely_pathogenic	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	PMS2	chr7	Frame_Shift_Del	DEL	c.1532delC	p.T511fs	0,0688592	Pathogenic	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	MET	chr7	Missense_Mutation	SNP	c.1132G>A	p.V378I	0,2225	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-1NAD126	BARD1	chr2	Missense_Mutation	DNP	c.1518_1519TG>CA	p.V507M	0,53012	Benign/Likely_benign	.	.	Uncertain significance	LP Pathogenic	
GERS26KLL0-1NAD126	BARD1	chr2	Missense_Mutation	DNP	c.1518_1519TG>CA	p.V507M	0,529991	Benign/Likely_benign	.	.	Uncertain significance	LP Pathogenic	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	APC	chr5	Nonsense_Mutation	SNP	c.1263G>A	p.W421*	0,197599	Pathogenic	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
ERS26BVAA-2TAD126	APC	chr5	Nonsense_Mutation	SNP	c.2805C>A	p.Y935*	0,156446	Pathogenic	Tier_II_potential	.	.	.	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	SDHB	chr1	Splice_Site	SNP	c.e3-1G>A	.	0,212106	Pathogenic	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	MSH6	chr2	Intron	INS	c.e2+31T>TTG	.	0,059542	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	Tier_IV_benign	.	
GERS262K3Z-2TAD126	TSC2	chr16	Intron	SNP	c.e10+7C>T	.	0,169492	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-2TAD126	ATM	chr11	Intron	SNP	c.e37-15G>C	.	0,486279	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	.	.	
GERS26V0U3-1NAD126	ATM	chr11	Intron	SNP	c.e37-15G>C	.	0,525362	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	.	Uncertain significance	HP Benign	
GERS26KLL0-2TAD126	RADS1C	chr17	Intron	SNP	c.e3+9G>C	.	0,435535	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_IV_benign	.	.	.	

GERS26KLL0-1NAD126	RAD51C	chr17	Intron	SNP	c.e3+9G>C	0,464684	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	Uncertain significance	IP Benign
GERS2678MML-1NAD126	MSH6	chr2	Intron	INS	c.e2+31T>TTG	0,267062	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	Uncertain significance	IP Benign
GERS2678MML-1NAD126	PTEN	chr10	5'UTR	SNP		0,52996	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	.	Benign	LP Benign
GERS2678MML-2TAD126	MSH6	chr2	Intron	INS	c.e2+31T>TTG	0,243952	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_IV_benign	.	
GERS2678MML-2TAD126	PTEN	chr10	5'UTR	SNP		0,559633	Conflicting_interpretations_of_pathogenicity	Tier_III_Uncertain	.	

Annex 2: GIPXplore testing: pre-analytical characterization (ICO cohort)

Sample ID	Volume plasma (ml)	Extracted cfDNA concentration (ng/μl)	Mass into Library Prep (ng)	Library concentration (ng/μl)
CH_1.1	4	0.421	14.735	341
CH_1.2	4	0.378	13.230	337
CH_1.3	3	0.383	13.405	353
CH_2.1	3.5	0.495	17.325	374
CH_2.2	3.5	0.648	22.680	409
CH_2.3	3.5	0.676	23.660	401
CH_3.1	4	0.440	15.400	374
CH_3.2	3	0.264	9.240	259
CH_4.1	4	0.403	14.105	325
CH_4.2	3.5	0.695	24.325	417
CH_4.3	4	0.914	31.990	381
CH_5.1	4	0.645	22.575	403
CH_5.2	2.5	0.419	14.665	353
CH_6.1	1	0.072	2.520	125
CH_6.2	4	0.639	22.365	388
CH_6.3	2	0.162	5.670	248
CH_7.1	4	0.286	10.010	305
CH_7.2	4	0.419	14.665	320
CH_7.3	4	0.370	12.950	387
CH_8.1	1	TOO LOW	TL*35ul	83.6
CH_8.2	4	0.329	11.515	308
CH_8.3	4	0.511	17.885	378
CH_9.1	1	TOO LOW	TL*35ul	64
CH_9.2	3	0.620	21.700	406
CH_9.3	4	0.521	18.235	404
CH_10.1	3	0.121	4.235	176
CH_10.2	4	0.270	9.450	296
CH_10.3	4	0.151	5.285	317
CH_11.1	4	0.489	17.115	372
CH_11.2	4	0.480	16.800	380
CH_12.1	4	1.450	50.750	450
CH_12.2	4	0.931	32.585	463
CH_13.1	4	0.202	7.070	249
CH_13.2	4	0.421	14.735	345
CH_13.3	4	0.296	10.360	306

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CH_14.1	3	0.165	5.775	211
CH_14.2	4	0.277	9.695	332
CH_14.3	2	0.197	6.895	293
CH_15.1	4	0.282	9.870	359
CH_15.2	4	0.618	21.630	387
CH_15.3	4	0.330	11.550	397
CH_16.1	4	0.240	8.400	352
CH_16.2	4	0.543	19.005	401
CH_17.1	4	0.585	20.475	452
CH_17.2	4	0.454	15.890	411
CH_17.3	4	0.614	21.490	430
CH_18.1	4	0.215	7.525	297
CH_18.2	4	0.546	19.110	485
CH_18.3	4	0.398	13.930	392
CH_19.1	4	0.279	9.765	377
CH_19.2	4	0.205	7.175	285
CH_19.3	3	0.256	8.960	343
CH_20.1	4	0.398	13.930	257
CH_20.2	4	0.334	11.690	397
CH_20.3	4	0.493	17.255	443
CH_21.1	4	0.319	11.165	361
CH_22.1	2	0.114	3.990	188
CH_23.1	4	0.099	3.465	172
CH_24.1	4	0.417	14.595	385

Samples prepared and sequenced